

Quality Evaluation Plan

The current document summarizes the main activities to ensure that the project will deliver outputs and results of high quality. Following what has been discussed and agreed among partners, it consists of the following categories:

Templates

- Partners have been asked to use specific templates for presenting the project or part(s) of it.
- Any report and intellectual output is based on specific templates, following the general rules set by the Erasmus+ Guide.
- Each partner has to fill in per semester two templates, one concerning the financial data and one on the actual progress made on the period. This is the most effective way to quantitatively monitor the project regularly and identify any risks, providing enough time for mitigation measures.

Meetings

- All partners have agreed to participate on all (three) physical meetings, to more efficiently contribute towards the project's evolution.
- Bi-monthly remote calls have been established from the very beginning to monitor the day-to-day work and identify progress, issues, deviations or other upcoming factors.
- Participation on the four workshops is realized through the conduction of open calls from the beginning of the project, where the best candidate profiles will be selected based on their innovative and feasible ideas. It has been agreed that in general each candidate will participate on up to two workshops, while in each workshop evaluation reports will be promoted in order to receive valuable feedback and improve the consequent workshops.
- Any other internal meeting (physical or remote) not contractually proposed is expected to take place in order to speed up the progress or solve unpredicted issues.

Outputs

- The Action Plan will be followed by each partner respecting their role as stated.

Erasmus+

ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ

ΙΔΡΥΜΑ
ΚΡΑΤΙΚΩΝ
ΥΠΟΤΡΟΦΙΩΝ

IKY

- The Gantt Chart will be also in general followed, but it may be fine-tuned according to the actual progress.
- The contractual intellectual outputs will be evaluated internally prior their finalization. In specific, the more complex ones will be mutually agreed on their contents and the way to be completed uniformly (specifically the four Case Studies).

Dissemination

- Four newsletters will have to be promoted during the project, one on each semester. This may be delayed for 1-2 months only if the inclusion of a project event might better support the upcoming newsletter.
- Each partner will disseminate the project to their internal and external networks. Moreover, they will state their preference on participating on upcoming events, and whenever necessary promote synergies among partners in several events.

Digital Educational Network For Cultural
Projects Implementation And Direction

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